

Large Area, Cost-Effective, and Ultra-Fast Fabrication of Mini-Coils Toward Noninvasive Magnetic Applications

Changhao Ge, Bhavani Prasad Yalagala, Tahereh Masalehdan, Mahdieh Shojaei Baghini, Danijela Gregurec, and Hadi Heidari*

Wearable and implantable coils are fundamental to advanced magnetic medical applications. Although the miniaturization of these coils facilitates their use in scenarios such as micromagnetic stimulation, wireless power transfer, and magnetic nanoparticle manipulation, the traditional microfabrication techniques are costly and nonenvironmentally friendly. This study presents a cleanroom-free, simple, quick, and low-cost fabrication method utilizing automated blade cutting to produce flexible mini-coils. The process is versatile; it can support various materials and substrates, and it enables rapid prototyping with batch production capabilities. The resulting coils are evaluated for mechanical durability, electrical and magnetic performance, and thermal behavior. Testing under various bending conditions and multiple bending cycles demonstrates the robustness and suitability for wearable applications. Additionally, their effectiveness in resistor-inductor filter and magnetic nanoparticles control highlights their adaptability. The findings affirm the promise of this method for producing customizable, sustainable, and scalable wearable electronic devices, paving the way for innovations in mobile healthcare technologies.

Miniaturized coils offer remarkable versatility and can be applied in diverse scenarios,^[3] such as micromagnetic stimulation,^[4] wireless power transfer for implanted devices,^[5] implantable heaters,^[6] and fine-tuning of the magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs)^[7] (Figure 1). Their reduced size brings distinct advantages, including greater flexibility in implementation, enhanced energy efficiency, and improved precision.^[1] As a result, the development of high-performance micro/mini-coils is gaining importance, presenting them as promising candidates for a broad range of emerging applications that require localized applications of variable magnetic fields.

The fabrication of flexible electronic devices, including mini-coils and microelectrodes, relies on a range of microfabrication techniques, such as through-silicon vias,^[8–10] laser,^[11,12] lithography,^[13,14] and micro-printing.^[15,16] These methods are known

for their precision, often achieving feature sizes down to the micron or nanometer scale, and have been effectively used in research to produce magnetic coils.^[17–20] However, they are also typically time-intensive and costly due to the reliance on specialized environments, such as cleanrooms, and the use of complex, high-cost equipment, like photolithography and metal deposition instruments. Additionally, advanced techniques such as photolithography generate significant chemical waste,^[21] involve toxic materials,^[22,23] and are highly energy-intensive.^[24] These factors not only escalate production costs but also raise environmental concerns, presenting a substantial challenge to the widespread implementation of magnetic coils. For these reasons, developing a cost-effective, environmentally friendly, and efficient method for producing miniaturized coils is of great significance. For applications involving wearable devices, the material and fabrication precision requirements are less stringent compared to those for implantable devices. This flexibility enables the exploration of more cost-effective and energy-efficient fabrication methods by tailoring performance standards to specific application needs, thereby significantly lowering production costs and minimizing environmental impact, which promotes the wider adoption of flexible magnetic coil technologies.

Here, a low-cost and rapid prototyping method for fabricating flexible mini-coils using an automated cutting blade technique is presented for the first time. This cleanroom-free process eliminates the need for costly, specialized environments and toxic chemicals, significantly reducing production costs. The method

1. Introduction

Wearable and implantable coils serve as a fundamental component in magnetic stimulation applications, playing a critical role in both research and clinical settings. With the growing emphasis on mobility in future healthcare technologies, designing coils optimized for wearable and implantable devices has become a key focus.^[1,2]

C. Ge, B. P. Yalagala, T. Masalehdan, M. S. Baghini, H. Heidari
Microelectronics Lab (meLAB)
School of Engineering
University of Glasgow
Glasgow G12 8QQ, UK
E-mail: hadi.heidari@glasgow.ac.uk

D. Gregurec
Biointerfaces lab
Faculty of Sciences
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg
Henkestraße 91, 91052 Erlangen, Germany

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.202501120>.

© 2025 The Author(s). Advanced Engineering Materials published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

DOI: 10.1002/adem.202501120

Figure 1. Conceptual figure for mini-coil applications and schematic representation of the fabrication methodology using automated blade cutting tools and its advantages.

offers material versatility, compatible with a wide range of substrates and conductive materials, to meet diverse requirements. Furthermore, including rapid prototyping enables quick design iterations and accelerated development cycles. Batch production is additionally feasible, allowing the fabrication in 5–10 s per sample. A comparison of consumption between the method and a conventional cleanroom fabrication process is given in **Table 1**. The method was successfully applied to create a flexible, wearable resistor-inductor filter (RL filter) design and actuate MNPs, both of which demonstrated the feasibility of the coils produced using this method for biomedical applications. This methodology lays the groundwork for the next generation of

flexible electronic devices, with potential applications in magnetic sensors, photodetectors, and antennas.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Design, Simulation, and Fabrication of Flexible Mini-Coil

The design of the mini-coils was carried out with varying spiral shapes, with programmable parameters such as inner and outer radius (r_i and r_o), number of turns (n), wire width (w), and spacing (s), as shown in **Figure 2**. Finite element modeling was carried

Table 1. Comparison between our cutter fabrication, laser fabrication, and cleanroom photolithography fabrication methods.

Property	Cleanroom fabrication	Lazer fabrication	Cutter fabrication
Fabrication environment	Cleanroom	Cleanroom free	Cleanroom free
Equipment cost	Cleanroom, photolithography, deposition, etc. (\$1 000 000 s level)	Laser equipment (\$100 000 s level)	Cutter (\$100 s level)
Material cost	Metal deposition (\$10 s per nm), photoresist (\$100 s per L)	Laser-processed substrate (\$10–100 s/ slice)	PVC sheets & Metal tapes (\$10 s level)
Fabrication time scales	2–4 day/1 wafer (10–100 s of samples)	20–60 min/sample	5–10 s/sample
Processing speeds	No (remake photomask needed)	Yes (programmable design)	Yes (programmable design)
Risk	Toxic chemicals used (e.g., TMAH)	Laser hazard	Low risk
Resolution	100 s nm– μ m level	10 s μ m	100–150 μ m

Figure 2. a) The editable parameters of a coil. 3D schematic diagram of a b) 10-turn rectangular coil, c) 10-turn hexagonal coil, d) 5-turn circular coil, e) 10-turn circular coil, and f) 15-turn circular coil. g) The average inductance value in the 10 kHz–1 MHz band of a 5, 10, 15-turn circular coil. h) The serial resistance of a 5, 10, 15-turn circular coil. i) The magnetic field of a 5, 10, 15-turn circular coil under a 10 Hz 100 mA current input.

out in COMSOL to analyze the thermal and magnetic characteristics, whilst the fabrication process was done using a digital blade cutting machine (Silhouette Cameo Cut), as illustrated in Figure 1 fabrication and advantages part. This machine is renowned for its precision, featuring a blade tip size of $\approx 100\ \mu\text{m}$ and a resolution of around $150\ \mu\text{m}$. As shown in Figure 1, conductive aluminum tape with properties includes contact resistance: $0.2\text{--}0.8\ \Omega\ \text{cm}^{-2}$, drift in resistance: $\pm 5\%$, thickness $60\ \mu\text{m}$, and oxide layer thickness $10\text{--}20\ \text{nm}$ was attached to flexible, thin, and transparent polyvinyl chloride (PVC) sheets ($80\ \mu\text{m}$ thickness, A4 size: $154 \times 242\ \text{mm}$), which was the substrate. Then, cut the aluminum layer using the digital blade cutter to form the flexible mini-coils. To ensure precise cutting, the Silhouette Studio software was used to adjust parameters, including blade depth, cutting force, cutting speed, and the number of passes. The optimized software settings included a blade depth of 3, a force of 24, and a speed of 3, as slower speeds and slightly higher forces were found to improve accuracy. Aluminum was chosen for its availability and cost-effectiveness, but the technique can also be translated to other conductive metal foils, such as copper (Cu) or silver (Ag). The parameters can be adjusted for thicker films to enable higher current capacities by increasing the cutting force and number of passes, making the technique versatile for diverse applications in flexible electronics. Various coil configurations were fabricated, including different numbers of turns (5, 10, 15, Figure 2d–f, and Figure S1a, Supporting Information), and shapes (circular, rectangular, hexagonal, Figure 2e, b, c, and Figure S1b, Supporting Information). Optimization of the blade-cutting parameters ensured uniform, well-defined patterns suitable for practical applications.

2.2. Mechanical Testing of Flexible Mini-Coil

Mechanical testing of the mini-coils was performed using two approaches. The first involved bending the coils over 3D-printed modules with radii corresponding to bending angles ranging from 30° to 180° . The second method subjected the coils to repetitive bending for up to 1,000 cycles. Postbending, I–V characteristics and inductance-capacitance-impedance (LCR) measurements were performed to evaluate the effects of mechanical strain, and parameters such as inductance, quality factor (Q-factor), and serial resistance were analyzed for all coil configurations to ensure uniformity by assessing their suitability for wearable applications.

2.3. Electrical, Thermal, and Magnetic Measurement of the Flexible Mini-Coil

Electrical testing included I–V characterization using a probe station inside a Faraday cage (Figure S3b, Supporting Information), connected to an Agilent Technologies source meter (2912 B, Figure S3a, Supporting Information). A compliance current of 100 mA and a voltage sweep from -500 to $+500\ \text{mV}$ were applied, managed by Easy Expert software. Inductance, Q-factor, and series resistance were measured using a Keysight E4980AL LCR meter, which was integrated with the probe station. Measurements were taken across a frequency range of 10 kHz to 1 MHz for all coil configurations. Thermal testing was conducted using an infrared (IR) camera attached to a probe station and regulated power supply (Figure S3c, Supporting Information). Coils were subjected to DC

currents ranging from low to high (up to 1.5 A), and thermal profiles were captured to analyze surface temperature. Magnetic testing involved using a tunnel magnetoresistance (TMR) sensor (TMR2104, sensitivity $0.0445 \text{ mV nT}^{-1}$, Figure S4b, Supporting Information), and the sinusoidal input signals (20–100 mA) were generated using a Keysight 6221 AC current source across frequencies from 10 Hz to 100 kHz (Figure S4A, Supporting Information). The data was read through Zurich Instruments MFLI Lock-in Amplifier (Figure S4c, Supporting Information), whilst the vertical magnetic field component was measured 4 mm above the coil surface center to simulate the depth of skin.

2.4. RL Filter LTSPICE Simulations and Hardware Testing

An RL filter was designed and simulated using LTspice (the circuit included a 1Ω source resistance in series with a 50Ω resistor and an inductor of $7 \mu\text{H}$ with an internal resistance (R_s) of 2Ω . AC sweep analysis was performed to evaluate frequency response characteristics. For hardware testing, an AIM-TTI function generator (TGF4242) provided the input AC signal, while a Tektronix 4-channel digital storage oscilloscope (DSO) recorded the output voltage. The input was applied at the resistor, and the output signal was measured across the inductor and series resistance configuration.

2.5. Tuning of MNP

The driving capability of circular micro-coils on MNPs was tested.^[25] These MNP coated with poly(maleic anhydride-*alt*-1-octadecene) (PMAO) of 110 nm in diameter (Figure 7a and b) exhibit vortex magnetization in their ground state, which aligns in plane with the direction of the magnetic field when applied, allowing for generating torques on a pN scale. In the experiment, a circular coil was placed beneath a glass slide with a water-based droplet containing a relatively high concentration of MNPs (1 mg mL^{-1}). A maximum current of 1 A was applied using an EL302RD current source. By manually switching the current, the magnetic field from the coil was alternately applied and removed to observe mechanical response of the nanoparticles to these field changes.

2.6. Preparation of Parylene C

Parylene C can be a very good film acting as a source of thermal energy absorber and helping in enhancing convective heat transfer to the surroundings.^[26] A transparent and ultra-thin Parylene C film of a thickness of $10 \mu\text{m}$ was deposited using the chemical vapor deposition process using the coating system from speciality coating systems company under high vacuum pressure of about 10^{-6} bar. The film was uniformly coated over the mini-coils in a more conformal way with a chamber with the substrate placed on one of the three stack layers of the substrate holders. The deposition process typically occurs in three layers: vaporization, pyrolysis, and deposition, and the deposition occurs at room temperature inside the chamber. The dimer was evaporated at $680\text{--}700^\circ\text{C}$ to turn from powder form to the gaseous form slowly, and finally, a thin layer of desired thickness (highly dependent on the weight of the dimer) was uniformly and

isotopically distributed across the chamber and coated on the substrate. A comparison between the coil before and after deposition is given in Figure S8, Supporting Information.

2.7. Statistical Analysis

The raw data obtained from the experiments were analyzed using the following processing methods to improve the reliability and reproducibility of the results. 6 batches (30 samples a batch) of samples (one batch of both 7, 12, and 17 mm circular coils, and three batches of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal shapes) were fabricated. Each parameter discussed below is performed by randomly selecting 3 samples from the corresponding batch and calculating their average value to improve the stability.

3. Experimental Results

The inductance, resistance, and magnetic field strength for prototype (circular shape) coils with different turns were evaluated to determine the optimal number of turns first, and then coils with this number of turns were fabricated in three shapes: circular, rectangular, and hexagonal. The three coil shapes were then evaluated based on key performance metrics, including intrinsic parameters such as inductance, resistance, factor, and external characteristics, such as heat generated and magnetic field strength. The intrinsic parameters directly influence the electromagnetic behavior and efficiency of the coils. For instance, inductance determines the frequency response, particularly in the higher frequency range of 10 kHz to 1 MHz, which is critical for applications like magnetic hyperthermia and wireless power transfer.^[27,28] The quality factor reflects the coil's efficiency and energy loss rate, while resistance impacts energy dissipation and heat generation. External metrics, such as temperature rise during operation and magnetic field strength, are critical for wearable applications to ensure safety, stability, and functionality. Since wearable coils often come into direct contact with the skin, temperature control is particularly crucial, while maintaining a stable magnetic field strength is essential for medical applications. Additionally, given that wearable devices frequently undergo bending and flexing during use, the coils were tested under various bending angles (on a 3D printed arch with 30° to 180° , Figure S5, Supporting Information) and repeated bending cycles (up to 1,000 cycles). These tests simulated real-world conditions to assess the durability and reliability of the coils. All these tests are performed by 3 repetitive experiments on 3 samples randomly selected from different batches to see how their average acts. As a result, the measurements focused on five key areas: optimizing the number of turns, coil performance under different bending angles, performance after multiple bending cycles, temperature rise under different current inputs, and magnetic field strength across varying current inputs. To ensure reliability, all measurements were averaged across three samples and were used to validate the proposed coil design while also offering valuable insights for future optimization and practical applications.

3.1. Optimization Studies on the Mini-Coils

Circular coils with 5, 10, and 15 turns, all featuring the same line width and spacing, were fabricated and evaluated (Figure 2d–f,

and Figure S1. a, Supporting Information). Three key parameters were analyzed and shown in Figure 2g–i: inductance (averaged over the 10 kHz–1 MHz frequency range), serial resistance (measured under DC conditions), and magnetic field strength at the coil center (measured with a 10 Hz, 100 mA sinusoidal input). These parameters are critical as they directly impact the coil's frequency response, thermal behavior, and magnetic performance. As shown in Figure 2g, the average inductance increased with the number of turns but only modestly, rising from $\approx 6 \mu\text{H}$ for the 5-turn coil to $7 \mu\text{H}$ for the 15-turn coil across the frequency range. Resistance, on the other hand, rose sharply with additional turns due to the linear growth in the outer diameter and the progressively greater wire length required for each subsequent turn (Figure 2h). Magnetic field strength at the coil center also increased with more turns, but the incremental gain diminished as the number of turns grew (Figure 2h). This diminishing return occurs because turns farther from the center contribute much less effectively to the central magnetic field, limiting the overall increase. Based on these results, the 10-turn coil proved to be the optimal configuration for wearable applications. While inductance varied only slightly, resistance and magnetic field strength were the decisive factors. The 10-turn coil strikes a balance between generating a strong magnetic field and producing manageable resistive heat. Therefore, in the following experiments, the 6 mm radius coils (Figure 2b, c, and e) are selected for further testing and analysis of different coil shapes.

3.2. Mechanical Bending Studies on Mini-Coils

For wearable applications, it is essential to evaluate coil performance under varying degrees of bending, as these devices must conform to the body's contours. To simulate such conditions, coils were secured onto 3D-printed modules with varying curvatures, representing potential use cases from the wrist to the thigh. The performance of three coil shapes—circular, rectangular, and hexagonal—was analyzed under different bending angles. Key parameters, including inductance, quality factor, and resistance, were measured and are presented in Figure 3. Figure 3a–c illustrates the variation of inductance with frequency (10 kHz to 1 MHz). Across all three shapes, inductance remained relatively consistent under bending. For angles below 150° , the inductance showed a sharp increase in the lower frequency range (10–100 kHz), stabilizing at $12\text{--}14 \mu\text{H}$ above 100 kHz. Beyond 150° , the inductance curves were steady, with minimal deviation, indicating high stability despite increased curvature. Figure 3d–f highlights the Q-factor variation with frequency. The Q factor increased with frequency, characteristic of inductors with low parasitic resistance. At bending angles below 150° , a noticeable dip in the Q factor was observed between 15 and 30 kHz, likely due to resonance caused by parasitic capacitance. As the bending angle increased, the effective inductance increased, shifting the resonant frequency lower and increasing the dip's impact. Angles exceeding 150° resulted in a smoother Q-factor curve. Given the significance of 100 kHz for applications like wireless power transfer, Figure 3j–l compares the inductance and Q factor for each shape at this frequency under different bending angles. Inductance remained stable across angles for all shapes, with the rectangular coil (Lr) showing slightly higher values than the

circular (Lc) and hexagonal (Lh) coils. In terms of Q factor, all shapes displayed a consistent trend of improvement with larger bending angles. However, the rectangular coil (Qr) typically exhibited a marginally lower Q factor associated with its higher resistance. Figure 3g–i show the current-voltage (I–V) responses and resistance values under DC input across bending angles. The I–V curves were symmetrical, with moderate bending angles ($60^\circ\text{--}90^\circ$) exhibiting broader current ranges. Resistance values varied significantly with bending, peaking at $\approx 4.0\text{--}4.5 \Omega$ for moderate angles, more than double the flat-state resistance (0°). The rectangular coil consistently exhibited resistance values 5%–10% higher than those of the other shapes, correlating with its slightly lower Q factor, despite its higher inductance. Overall, the inductance of the coils remained stable across all bending conditions, while the Q factor improved with larger angles, and the resistance exhibited the most variation, peaking at moderate bending angles. Among the three shapes, the rectangular coil demonstrated the highest inductance but faced trade-offs in Q factor due to increased resistance. These results confirm the robustness of the coils under bending conditions and their suitability for wearable applications.

3.3. Mechanical Characteristics of the Minicoils

In wearable applications, devices are subject to repeated folding due to the wearer's movements, making it critical to understand the impact of these bending cycles on performance and durability. To simulate such conditions, electrical characteristics were recorded after every 100 bending cycles until 1,000 bending cycles for circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coil shapes. Each bending cycle began with the coil in a flat state, followed by bending to a 180-degree arch, and returning to the flat state. Key metrics—inductance, quality factor, and resistance—are presented in Figure 4. Figure 4a–c illustrates the inductance variation with frequency (10 to 100 kHz) across different bending cycles. All coil shapes exhibited similar frequency response, with inductance values decreasing slightly as frequency increased. Initially ranging from $7.0\text{--}7.5 \mu\text{H}$ at lower frequencies, inductance dropped to $5.5\text{--}6.0 \mu\text{H}$ at higher frequencies. Repeated bending cycles caused a gradual decrease in inductance, with reductions of $\approx 0.7 \mu\text{H}$ for circular coils, $0.4 \mu\text{H}$ for rectangular coils, and $0.5 \mu\text{H}$ for hexagonal coils. The circular coil exhibited the most pronounced decline. Figure 4d–f shows the variation in the quality factor with frequency for the three coil shapes under different bending cycles. The quality factor increased with frequency for all shapes. The quality factor improved during the first 200–300 cycles. Figure 4g–i depicts the current-voltage (I–V) relationships and resistance values for the three coil shapes under different bending cycles. The resistance value exhibited minor fluctuations, remaining within 1.5 to 2.0Ω across all cycles. Among the three shapes, the rectangular coil demonstrated the most stable resistance, while the circular and hexagonal coils showed slightly greater variations. At 100 kHz, the electrical characteristics of the coils revealed minimal differences in inductance across the three shapes. Inductance initially increased slightly, reaching $\approx 6.5 \mu\text{H}$, before gradually declining after 500 cycles and stabilizing at around $6.0 \mu\text{H}$. The quality factor initially rose from 1.5 to 2.25 within the first 300 cycles.

Figure 3. The coil characteristics under different bending angles. a–c) Inductance value of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils over 10 kHz–1 MHz. d–f) Quality factor of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils over 10 kHz–1 MHz. g–i) I–V curve of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coil from –0.5 to 0.5 V. j) Inductance value (standard deviation) of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coil at 100 kHz. k) Quality factor (standard deviation) of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils at 100 kHz. l) Serial resistance (standard deviation) of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils under a DC source.

Beyond 400 cycles, different trends emerged: the circular coil's quality factor decreased slightly to about 2.0, the rectangular coil rose above 2.5, peaking at 3.0 around 600 cycles, and the hexagonal coil stabilized near 2.25 with minor oscillations. Compared to the newly manufactured coils described in the previous section,

the inductance initially dropped significantly, from 12 to 7.5 μH within the first 100 cycles, but it is comparable to the result in the number of turns optimization and remained stable and consistent through 1,000 cycles. The quality factor not only exceeded its initial value under unbent conditions but also improved steadily

Figure 4. The coil characteristics under different bending cycles. a–c) Inductance value of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils over 10 kHz–1 MHz. d–f) Quality factor of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils over 10 kHz–1 MHz. g–i) I–V curve of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils from –0.5 to 0.5 V. j) Inductance value (standard deviation) of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils at 100 kHz. k) Quality factor (standard deviation) of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils at 100 kHz. l) Serial resistance (standard deviation) of circular, rectangular, and hexagonal coils under DC source.

with repeated cycles, likely due to changes in resistance and parasitic capacitance effects. Compared to the results in Section 3.2, repeated bending cycles may enhance the coil’s performance within this frequency range by mitigating resonant effects. Resistance showed minimal variation and stayed comparable

to that of the newly manufactured coils, further confirming the durability of the designs. Finally, these results suggest that the coils are highly reliable under repeated bending cycles, maintaining stable electrical characteristics with minimal degradation, making them suitable for long-term wearable applications.

3.4. Temperature Response to Current

The temperature response is a critical metric for wearable devices due to its direct impact on safety. This study investigated the thermal performance of the coils under extreme conditions, particularly resistive heating when the input current exceeded 1 A. Figure 5a–c present COMSOL simulations of surface temperature distribution for the three coil shapes under 1.5 A and for 3 seconds. Across all shapes, the highest temperatures were observed near the center of the coils, reflecting the concentration of current density. The circular coil demonstrated the lowest surface temperature, ranging from 70 to 80 °C, followed by the hexagonal coil for temperatures between 90 to 110 °C. The rectangular coil exhibited the highest temperature, ranging from 120 to 140 °C, likely due to its higher resistance. Figure 5d–f show experimental temperature measurements using an IR camera for different current levels. The temperature increased consistently with higher input currents across all coil shapes. The experimental results closely aligned with the simulations: the rectangular coil exhibited the highest average temperature, exceeding 100 °C at 1.5 A; the hexagonal coil reached around 90 °C; the circular coil maintained the lowest temperature, around 80 °C. While the trends in the experimental and simulation data were consistent, slight discrepancies were observed. These differences are likely due to the IR camera measuring surface temperatures indirectly, which may result in slightly lower recorded values compared to actual coil surface temperatures. The findings highlight the significant influence of coil geometry on thermal performance. The circular coil exhibited superior thermal behavior, with lower temperatures. Conversely, the rectangular coil's higher temperatures may limit its use in scenarios requiring prolonged or high-current operation. However, in most practical applications,

AC signals are the primary choice, and the heat generation is significantly reduced, expanding the safe operational range of these coils. Therefore, for all these designs, a current input of less than 1 A should be regarded as safe.

3.5. Magnetic Field Response to Current and Frequency

The magnetic field, as the primary factor interacting with tissues, directly determines the device's effectiveness. To evaluate magnetic field strength, the coils were tested using a TMR sensor under various frequencies and amplitudes of sinusoidal input signals. Measurements were taken on a plane 4 mm above the coil surface, approximating typical skin thickness. Figure 6a–c illustrates the COMSOL simulation results for magnetic field distribution 4 mm above the coil surface with a DC input of 100 mA. Each coil shape exhibited distinct magnetic field characteristics: the circular coil produced a relatively uniform field distribution with a larger coverage area but the weakest central field strength (150–160 μ T); the hexagonal coil showed slightly higher field concentration and moderately stronger central field strength (160–170 μ T); the rectangular coil demonstrated the highest field convergence, generating the strongest central magnetic field (180–200 μ T). Figure 6g–i presents 3D bar charts of experimentally measured magnetic field strength for the three coil shapes, illustrating the relationships among current, frequency, and field strength. Across all coil types, magnetic field strength increased with higher input currents and lower frequencies. The field strength increased almost linearly with current, while frequency had a nonlinear influence. Magnetic field strength declined negligibly between 10 Hz and 10 kHz, but dropped significantly from 10 to 100 kHz. At low frequencies (below 100 Hz), the

Figure 5. The surface temperature distribution in COMSOL with 1.5 A current input of a) circular, b) rectangular, and c) hexagonal coil. The measured temperature in IR camera (95% convince interval) of d) circular, e) rectangular, and f) hexagonal coil.

Figure 6. The magnetic field distribution at plane 4 mm above a) circular, b) rectangular, and c) hexagonal coil. The magnetic field magnitude and direction in vertical x - z and y - z planes cross section of d) circular, e) rectangular, and f) hexagonal coil. The measured magnetic field strength by TMR sensor of g) circular, h) rectangular, and i) hexagonal coils under different current inputs.

rectangular coil outperformed the others, producing a magnetic field $\approx 20\%$ stronger. However, its magnetic field decreased more rapidly with increasing frequency. In contrast, the circular coil exhibited better performance at higher frequencies, with a slower decline in field strength. The hexagonal coil showed the greatest stability, maintaining minimal decline across the frequency range. Between 10 Hz and 10 kHz, the magnetic field strength decreased by $\approx 40\%$ for the rectangular coil, 25% for the circular coil, and 10% for the hexagonal coil. The discrepancies from the simulation results may stem from the directional limitations of the TMR sensor, which can only focus on the main component of the magnetic field. According to Figure 6d–f, at the center area of the coils, the

main component of the magnetic field is in perpendicular direction of the surface of the coil. Meanwhile, the uniformity of magnetic field distribution of circular coil mentioned above is reflected in another perspective.

4. Application of Mini-Coil as High Pass Filter

4.1. Resistive-Inductor (RL)-Based Passive High Pass Filter (HPF)

The fabricated mini-coils were utilized to design a RL-based HPF, suitable for a wide range of applications. **Figure 7.**

Figure 7. a) The experiment setup and corresponding equivalent circuit of RL filter. b) The frequency response curve from simulation and recorded data. c) Select 1 MHz as an example to show the gain (−5 dB on dashed line in b) of the output voltage.

A illustrates the schematic of the RL-based passive HPF, consisting of an input AC voltage source (V_s), a resistor (R), and an inductor (L_s) in series. The performance of the HPF was evaluated using a SPICE-based simulator to analyze its frequency response. Two key parameters, gain (G) and cut-off frequency (f_c), were considered critical for assessing filter performance.

$$G = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{V_o}{V_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$f_c = \frac{R}{2\pi L_s} \quad (2)$$

The hardware was tested with a function generator providing a sine wave input of 1 V amplitude (2 V peak-to-peak). The output was measured across a 10-turn circular coil connected in series with a 50 Ω resistor, using a DSO. Figure 7b and c compare the frequency response characteristics from simulations and experiments, plotting gain versus frequency over a range of 10 kHz to 10 MHz. Approximately, the gain of 0 dB at high frequencies in the MHz range was recorded. f_c is around 1.1 MHz, closely matching the theoretical value from Equation (2). Experimental results closely aligned with theoretical simulations. The transfer function

of the RL circuit was used to calculate the rise time of the HPF, which was determined to be 23 ms, indicating a quick response to signal excitations. A slight deviation in gain at lower frequencies was observed, attributed to the white noise, parasitic capacitance, and inherent series resistance of the mini-coil inductors, as discussed in previous sections. The mini-coil-based HPF demonstrates excellent filtering capabilities with a maximum gain of 0 dB, making it highly suitable for high-speed and high-frequency applications. The quick response and robust performance validate the potential of these flexible mini-coils for use in advanced electronics, particularly in fields requiring compact and efficient filtering solutions.

4.2. Actuation of MNPs

MNPs have been widely applied in various fields, including drug delivery, magnetic hyperthermia, and mechanical or thermal neural stimulation. One of the significant application scenarios for wearable mini-coils is enabling precise control of MNPs to deliver mechanical stimulation through their movement.^[1] The torques generated in single vortex-containing particles are achieved at very low (<20 Hz) frequencies. The mini-coils here

drive MNPs at a manually controlled switching on/off frequency (≈ 1 Hz), which allows for clearer visualization of their micromotions under an alternating field. This magnetic force-based mechanical micromovement, driven by fields of 1–2 mT at a skin-depth distance, is a crucial validation step for the design’s potential practical applications. The experimental setup is shown in **Figure 8c** and **Figure S6**, Supporting Information. Place the coil beneath a glass slide and connect it to a 1 A current source. A water-based droplet containing MNPs is dipped near the center of the coil and left undisturbed for a period to allow the MNPs to stabilize at the glass surface. The power source is then toggled on and off, and the MNPs’ responses at the moments of switching are observed under a microscope. The MNP motion is depicted in **Figure 8d**. Initially, MNPs are randomly aggregated and oriented due to their magnetic properties in concentrated solutions. However, when an external magnetic field is applied, the MNPs align to maintain consistency with the direction of the external field, thereby driving the movement of the MNPs and causing a spatial shift. **Figure 8e, f**, and the video in **Figure S7**, Supporting Information, demonstrate that MNPs exhibit clear and significant responses to the current source on or off. This confirms that coils fabricated using this method can effectively drive nanoparticles. However, from **Figure 8e** and **f**, it can be observed that the most obvious movement occurs in the smaller branches (like **Figure 8a**) of the MNP clusters. This is because the larger aggregated clusters (like **Figure 8b**), though also move, have higher mass and more complex interactions between particles, which limit their motion. As shown in **Supplementary Video**, **Figure S7**,

Supporting Information, even though the movement amplitude is limited, larger clusters still exhibit visible motion. Additionally, **Figure S7**, Supporting Information, illustrates that the movement amplitude gradually diminishes over time because of the unidirectional current input, which generates a magnetic field in only one direction. When the current is applied, particles align with the external magnetic field from their initial random orientations. When the current is turned off, the magnetic field is removed, eliminating the aligning torque. Consequently, the particles tend to remain stationary rather than returning to their original positions. As a result, with repeated application and removal of the magnetic field, more particles stay aligned, leading to a reduction in the overall movement amplitude.

5. Discussion

The experimental performance of the coils closely aligned with theoretical predictions, in terms of temperature, magnetic field, and filtering characteristics. As shown in **Section 4.2**, the inductance decreases with decreasing frequency in the low-frequency range, and this reduction becomes less pronounced as the bending angle increases. When the bending angle exceeds 150 degrees, this reduction is effectively mitigated. Additionally, the quality factor displayed distinct dips at lower frequencies, which disappeared when the bending angle exceeded 150 degrees. In **Section 4.6**, deviations from theoretical frequency responses at lower frequencies were also observed in the filters. These observations suggest the possible presence of parasitic capacitance in the coils, while

Figure 8. Nanoparticles under scanning electron microscope in a) branch state and b) cluster state. c) The setup of the tuning experiment. d) The mechanism of MNPs tuning. e,f) optical microscope pictures of MNPs before and after a magnetic field applied through a mini-coil, with response time and displacement distance marked.

the findings in Section 4.3 indicate that repeated bending may help eliminate the resonant effect. The thermal and magnetic simulation results showed strong consistency with experimental data. Differences between simulation and measurement results may stem from two primary factors: (1) the IR camera measures temperature indirectly, rather than the exact surface temperature of the coil, and (2) the TMR sensor measures only the strongest magnetic field component in a single direction, rather than the magnitude of the overall field strength. Nevertheless, the consistent trends observed in qualitative analysis affirm the reliability of the results. Significant differences in thermal and magnetic performance were observed among the three coil geometries. The rectangular coil demonstrated sensitivity to bending and instability, along with the most pronounced Joule heating effect, which are consistent with its higher resistance observed in LCR measurements. While the rectangular coil produced the strongest central magnetic field at low frequencies, its high heat output may limit its suitability for wearable applications. The hexagonal coil exhibited similar magnetic field performance to the circular coil, with slightly higher magnetic field strength and lower sensitivity to frequency changes, though it generated slightly more heat than the circular coil. The final two application experiments not only validate the previous coil measurements but also demonstrate the potential versatility of these coils, further highlighting the value of this rapid production method. However, it should be acknowledged that the scenarios simulated in these experiments are simplified. For practical applications, the coil's size, shape, material, substrate, and other parameters must be tailored to suit specific use cases and application environments.

6. Conclusion

This study proposed a new manufacturing method for wearable coils, which enables the rapid and cost-effective production of flexible mini-coils. The stability and feasibility of the coils were demonstrated through practical applications. This method offers excellent material versatility, requires no specialized environment or equipment, and supports the rapid, large-scale production of samples to facilitate optimization to meet the needs of customization. Furthermore, this approach can be extended to the fabrication of other wearable electronic devices, contributing to future mobile healthcare.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European CROSSBRAIN project, funded by the European Union's European Innovation Council called HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDERCHALLENGES-01-02, under grant agreement no 101070908 and BRAINSTORM, called HORIZON-EIC-2022-PATHFINDEROPEN-01, under grant agreement no. 101099355.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Changhao Ge: conceptualization (lead); data curation (lead); formal analysis (lead); investigation (lead); methodology (lead); validation (lead); writing—original draft (lead). **Bhavani Prasad Yalagala:** conceptualization (equal); data curation (equal); formal analysis (equal); investigation (lead); methodology (lead); supervision (supporting); validation (lead); visualization (equal); writing—original draft (lead); writing—review and editing (lead). **Tahereh Masalehdan:** data curation (supporting); formal analysis (supporting); validation (supporting). **Mahdieh Shojaei Baghini:** investigation (supporting); methodology (supporting). **Danijela Gregurec:** conceptualization (equal); formal analysis (supporting); supervision (equal); validation (equal); writing—original draft (supporting); writing—review and editing (supporting). **Hadi Heidari:** conceptualization (lead); formal analysis (lead); funding acquisition (lead); investigation (lead); project administration (lead); resources (lead); software (lead); supervision (lead); validation (lead); visualization (lead); writing—review and editing (lead).

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

Keywords

electronics, flexible, healthcare, magnetic nanoparticles, microfabrication, mini-coil, wearable

Received: April 25, 2025

Revised: August 3, 2025

Published online: September 7, 2025

- [1] C. Ge, T. Masalehdan, M. S. Baghini, V. D. Toro, L. Signorelli, H. Thomson, D. Gregurec, H. Heidari, *Adv. Sci.* **2024**, *11*, 2404254.
- [2] E. McGlynn, V. Nabaie, E. Ren, G. Galeote-Checa, R. Das, G. Curia, H. Heidari, *Adv. Sci.* **2021**, *8*, 2002693.
- [3] Y. Song, J. Min, W. Gao, *ACS Nano* **2019**, *13*, 12280.
- [4] G. G. Westin, B. D. Bassi, S. H. Lisanby, B. Luber, *Clin. Neurophysiol.* **2014**, *125*, 142.
- [5] S. R. Khan, S. K. Pavuluri, G. Cummins, M. P. Y. Desmulliez, *Sensors* **2020**, *20*, 3487.
- [6] G. S. Cañón Bermúdez, A. Krav, T. Voitsekhivska, I. Hochnadel, A. Lebanov, A. Potthoff, J. Fassbender, T. Yevsa, D. Makarov, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* **2019**, *21*, 1900407.
- [7] H. Huang, S. Delikanli, H. Zeng, D. M. Ferkey, A. Pralle, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2010**, *5*, 602.
- [8] Z. Wang, *Microelectron. Eng.* **2019**, *210*, 35.
- [9] M. J. K. Klein, T. Ono, M. Esashi, J. G. Korvink, *J. Micromech. Microeng.* **2008**, *18*, 075002.
- [10] C. Zhuo, C. Baixin, *2017 China Semiconductor Technology Inter. Conf. (CSTIC)*, **2017**.
- [11] R. You, Y. Q. Liu, Y. L. Hao, D. D. Han, Y. L. Zhang, Z. You, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32*, 1901981.
- [12] L. Yang, J. Wei, Z. Ma, P. Song, J. Ma, Y. Zhao, Z. Huang, M. Zhang, F. Yang, X. Wang, *Nanomaterials* **2019**, *9*, 1789.

- [13] D. R. Hines, N. P. Siwak, L. A. Mosher, R. Ghodssi, *MEMS Lithography And Micromachining Techniques* (Eds: R. Ghodssi, P. Lin), Springer US, Boston, MA **2011**.
- [14] D. Qin, Y. Xia, G. M. Whitesides, *Nat. Protoc.* **2010**, *5*, 491.
- [15] J. A. Lewis, G. M. Gratson, *Mater. Today* **2004**, *7*, 32.
- [16] D. A. Pardo, G. E. Jabbour, N. Peyghambarian, *Adv. Mater.* **2000**, *12*, 1249.
- [17] S. W. Lee, S. I. Fried, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* **2017**, *25*, 1375.
- [18] S. W. Lee, S. I. Fried, in *2015 7th Inter. IEEE/EMBS Conf. on Neural Engineering (NER)* **2015**.
- [19] A. Khalifa, M. Zaeimbashi, T. X. Zhou, S. M. Abrishami, N. Sun, S. Park, T. Šumarac, J. Qu, I. Zohar, A. Yacoby, S. Cash, N. X. Sun, *Microsyst. Nanoeng.* **2021**, *7*, 91.
- [20] M. E. Rizou, T. Prodromakis, *Biomed. Phys. Eng. Express* **2018**, *4*, 25016.
- [21] E. Vozzola, M. Overcash, E. Griffing, *PDA J. Pharm. Sci. Technol.* **2018**, *72*, 236.
- [22] J. Li, Y.-F. Zhou, *Toxicol. Ind. Health* **2015**, *31*, 123.
- [23] V. Innocenzi, S. B. Zueva, N. M. Ippolito, F. Ferella, M. Prisciandaro, F. Vegliò, *Chemosphere* **2022**, *307*, 135913.
- [24] K. Kircher, X. Shi, S. Patil, K. M. Zhang, *Energy Build.* **2010**, *42*, 282.
- [25] D. Gregurec, A. W. Senko, A. Chuvilin, P. D. Reddy, A. Sankaraman, D. Rosenfeld, P.-H. Chiang, F. Garcia, I. Tafel, G. Varnavides, *ACS Nano* **2020**, *14*, 8036.
- [26] J. Yao, W. Qiang, X. Guo, H. Fan, Y. Zheng, Y. Xu, X. Yang, *Sensors* **2021**, *21*, 1107.
- [27] A. G. Roca, B. Wiese, J. Timmis, G. Vallejo-Fernandez, K. O'Grady, *IEEE Trans. Mag.* **2012**, *48*, 4054.
- [28] Z. Zhang, K. T. Chau, C. Qiu, C. Liu, *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.* **2015**, *30*, 5237.